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**PUBLIC HEALTH – FIGHTING HEALTH INEQUALITIES
AT EVERY AGE IN EVERY COUNTRY**

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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Artificial intelligence in public health

Abstract 1

Are AI, AR and VR the key to a healthier society?

Czy AI, AR i VR są kluczem do zdrowszego społeczeństwa?

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Keywords: AI, augmented reality, virtual reality, health

Introduction: The dynamic development of artificial intelligence (AI) is opening up new possibilities in public health. AI is capable of processing massive amounts of data in a way that surpasses human analytical capabilities, making it a powerful tool in prediction, diagnosis, and personalization. INNOVATIVE VISUAL TECHNOLOGIES, SUCH AS AUGMENTED REALITY (AR) AND VIRTUAL REALITY (VR), ARE ALSO PLAYING AN INCREASING ROLE, COMPLEMENTING THE CAPABILITIES OF AI IN PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS.

Data and methodology: PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS OF AI, AR, AND VR: AI can analyze data from various sources (social media, wearable data) to detect and predict the spread of infectious diseases early. Additionally, AI supports hospital management and optimizes resource allocation, which increases system efficiency. AI algorithms can analyze patients' genetic and behavioral data to create personalized treatment plans and preventive programs. In this context, VR and AR are used in psychological therapy (e.g., treating phobias and PTSD) and rehabilitation. Virtual reality allows the creation of controlled therapeutic environments, while augmented reality can overlay digital information on the real world, supporting patients in their daily exercises.

Conclusions: The implementation of artificial intelligence, augmented reality, and virtual reality in public health offers significant potential for improving the quality and accessibility of care, as well as revolutionizing education and therapy. At the same time, a thoughtful and ethical approach to their implementation is necessary to avoid negative consequences, such as deepening inequalities and violating privacy. THE FUTURE OF THESE TECHNOLOGIES IN PUBLIC HEALTH DEPENDS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF APPROPRIATE LEGAL REGULATIONS AND ETHICAL STANDARDS THAT WILL PROTECT PATIENTS AND GUARANTEE THE FAIR USE OF INNOVATIONS.

Abstract 2

Artificial intelligence in trichology: opportunities and threats from the viewpoint of healthy aging.

„Sztuczna inteligencja w trychologii: szanse i zagrożenia z perspektywy zdrowego starzenia się.

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Keywords: Artificial intelligence, healthy aging, medical staff, seniors, trichology

Introduction: AI holds vast opportunities for any human activity and this may apply to trichology, which is a specific domain combining concepts from medicine and cosmetology. Trichology globally and in Poland, offers variety of services targeted on elderly customers who want to keep their head scalp skin and hair in sound condition. The objective of this study is to assess how opportunities and threats of AI use in trichology are identified among trichology professionals (medical and managerial staff).

Data and methodology: Due to the novelty of the undertaken topic, the evidence for the structure and substance of opportunities and threats of using AI in trichology from the perspective of healthy aging, the authors have produced qualitative data with the use of interviews conducted among various professionals working in Hairmitage LTD, a trichology clinic operating in four cities in Poland. This means that the authors have opted for surveying as the research method to deal with empirical challenges imposed in this study. The research tool is the interview questionnaire that consists of ten key questions linked to the previously stated research objective.

Results: The participants expressed diverse opinions on the linkage between the AI in trichology and healthy aging. For the elderly customers, this may deliver various positive outcomes, specifically in better diagnostics and treatment handling and monitoring. However, what they are wary of, is the risk of depersonalized treatment, where AI cannot replace humans, not to add fear that AI may be still susceptible to erred functioning.

Conclusions: As a final remark for this research study, qualitative data collected from the opinions of various persons working in Hairmitage trichology clinic, managers and medical professionals should be willing to introduce and further expand the practice of AI use in trichological services, however, what they should bear in mind is that the AI tools work effectively and flawlessly. Also, trichology specialists should be sensitive to the topic of feelings and attitudes of elderly customers, as their positions towards presence of sometimes 'crewless' service solution may vary.

Abstract 3

Artificial intelligence to improve the health of older people - analysis of attitudes and identification of barriers to the acceptance of new technologies

Sztuczna inteligencja w poprawie zdrowia osób starszych – analiza postaw i identyfikacja barier w akceptacji nowych technologii

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Keywords: artificial intelligence, gerontechnology, senior health, technology acceptance, healthcare

Introduction: The use of artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare offers a promising perspective for improving the quality of life of older adults. However, the effective implementation of these technologies is socially contingent and largely depends on their acceptance by end users. The primary goal of this study was to assess the level of acceptance and identify key attitudes, perceived benefits, and barriers related to the use of AI solutions in healthcare among the senior population.

Data and methodology: A pilot study was conducted using a diagnostic survey method. The sample was purposive and included 162 senior patients (over 65 years of age) from a clinic in Katowice. The research tool was a proprietary questionnaire, and the collected data were statistically analyzed using Statistica software.

Results: The overall acceptance of AI solutions among respondents was low at 34%. Medication reminder apps had the highest acceptance (61%), while autonomous diagnostic systems had the lowest (9%). The main perceived benefits were an increased sense of security (72%) and improved adherence to medical recommendations (64%). The dominant barriers were concerns about data loss and privacy (81%), difficulty using the technology (76%), and a lack of trust in machine-based diagnoses (73%).

Conclusions: Despite the perceived benefits, the level of AI acceptance among seniors remains low. Key challenges in designing solutions for this user group include ensuring data privacy, an intuitive interface, and engaging medical staff in building trust in new technologies.

Abstract 4

Readability and Citation Practices of AI-Generated Health Information on Human Metapneumovirus: Implications for Public Health Communication

Czytelność i praktyki cytowania treści zdrowotnych generowanych przez sztuczną inteligencję na temat ludzkiego metapneumowirusa: implikacje dla komunikacji w zdrowiu publicznym

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Keywords: artificial intelligence, chatbots, readability, health communication, human metapneumovirus

Introduction: This study examined the readability and citation practices of AI-generated responses to questions about human metapneumovirus (hMPV), an emerging respiratory virus of public health concern. As AI chatbots increasingly disseminate medical information, ensuring their outputs are clear, transparent, and evidence-based is essential to strengthening trust, accessibility, and equity in digital health communication.

Data and methodology: Four artificial intelligence chatbots (ChatGPT-4, Copilot, Gemini, and Grok) were asked 14 standardized questions derived from guidelines of the World Health Organization, the Centers

for Disease Control and Prevention, and the National Health and Medical Research Council. Anonymized responses were analyzed for readability, citation frequency, and source credibility using non-parametric statistical tests ($p < 0.05$).

Results: A total of 56 chatbot responses were analyzed. Only one met the American Medical Association’s recommended readability level (6th–7th grade). Median readability scores ranged from grade 10.4 to 16.0, indicating that most responses were too complex for lay audiences; Chatbot C produced the most readable outputs, whereas Chatbot D generated the least accessible ones. Only two chatbots provided citations—one referencing 68 reliable sources, mainly from health organizations and academic institutions, and another listing 31 sources of mixed reliability.

Conclusions: AI-generated health information often exceeds recommended readability levels and lacks consistent citation practices, reducing comprehension and trust among users with limited health literacy. Enhancing accessibility and credibility requires readability optimization, plain-language defaults, and real-time citation tools. These innovations can promote equitable access to reliable health information and align AI technologies with ethical standards in public health communication.

Abstract 5

Ethical Risks Associated with the Use of AI in Public Health

Etyczne zagrożenia związane z wykorzystaniem AI w zdrowiu publicznym.

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Keywords: Artificial intelligence, public health, ethics, data bias, safety.

Introduction: Artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming an increasingly important tool in public health, offering opportunities to improve diagnostics, treatment, and the analysis of epidemiological data. At the same time, its application raises significant ethical questions, including the risk of inequality in access to medical services, breaches of patient privacy, and decisions made based on algorithmic outputs. The aim of this paper is to analyze potential ethical risks associated with AI in public health and to identify practical implications for health policy and system design.

Data and methodology: The analysis is based on a review of scientific literature concerning the use of AI in public health, as well as documents outlining ethical regulations and guidelines in this field. Additionally, an ethical risk assessment was conducted, considering aspects such as patient data privacy, algorithmic transparency, and data bias—that is, situations in which training data reflect social inequalities or historical prejudices, potentially leading to discriminatory decisions made by AI systems.

Results: The analysis revealed that AI can significantly improve the efficiency of public health systems by enabling rapid processing of large datasets, forecasting epidemiological trends, and supporting clinical decision-making. However, several serious ethical risks were identified, including the potential for

deepening health inequalities, limiting patient privacy, and lacking full algorithmic transparency. Data bias proved to be a particularly important issue when AI systems were trained on unevenly represented populations, which can result in inadequate or unfair medical recommendations. Furthermore, the absence of consistent regulations for AI implementation in healthcare means that these systems are often deployed without sufficient external oversight.

Conclusions: The implementation of AI in public health offers substantial benefits but also poses significant ethical challenges. To minimize risks, systems must be designed in accordance with principles of transparency, accountability, and equitable access, while ensuring continuous monitoring of training data quality to reduce bias. Health policies and regulations should emphasize patient privacy protection and include mechanisms for algorithm auditing to ensure that technology supports fair and ethical healthcare delivery.

Health policy and social justice

Abstract 6

Changes in the characteristics of hospitalized cardiac patients in the peak of COVID-19 pandemic

Zmiany w charakterystyce pacjentów kardiologicznych w szczycie pandemii COVID-19

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Keywords: health crisis, pandemia, availability, cardiology

Introduction: The pandemic of COVID-19 changed the quantity and quality of patients hospitalized in specialist Departments worldwide, including cardiology. In Poland, data on the mortality during COVID-19 pandemic according to web statistics (<https://koronawirusunas.pl>) indicate the first period of 2021 to be burdened with the highest mortality from COVID-19 and comorbidities with subsequent highest influence on the organization of care. Such circumstance merits deep understanding of temporal quality of care regarding the standard of care in order to prepare for potential epidemic emergency in the future.

Data and methodology: This retrospective analysis presents the characteristics of consecutive patients hospitalized in a tertiary cardiac, non-COVID, center in Upper Silesia region, Poland during the peak of COVID-19 pandemic in regard to representative dataset from pre-pandemic period based on data from Polish Ministry of Health (PMH).

Results: From Jan 1st to March 31st 2021 the total of 288 patients were hospitalized and 275 of them (95%) entered the analysis. This was much less than in representative periods of 2019 and 2020 (mean 509 hospitalizations). Median age of hospitalized patients was 70 (21-98) years. Regarding the pre-pandemic period of 2016 and data from PMH, there was a similar rate of patients over 65 years (65% vs. 67%), women were less represented during pandemic (39% vs 50%) and median duration of hospital stay was shorter (5 vs 7.1 days). The most frequent admission diagnosis in 2021 was decompensated heart failure (97 patients, 35%) and acute myocardial infarction (AMI, 86 patients, 31%). Further, patients were admitted with atrial fibrillation (37 patients, 13%), tachy- and bradyarrhythmias (18, 6.5%), other cardiac causes (10, 3.6%) and other diagnosis (27, 10%) (Figure 1). The structure of hospitalized population differed significantly in 2016 with less acute admissions (Figure 2). Urgent admissions reached 75% vs. 62% in 2016. Patients suffered from mean 5 ± 2 comorbidities and 91% of patients were characterised with multimorbidity, while only 72% was defined as median to very-high morbidity index in 2016. Among patients with final diagnosis of AMI 43 patients (91%) received invasive treatment, which was higher than in 2016 (86.1%). In-hospital survival rate was 99.6%.

Conclusions: Pandemia of COVID-19 caused a significant shift in quality and quantity of the hospitalized population in high reference cardiac center, defined by high prevalence of acute disorders and multimorbidity, with sustained high availability, quality and efficacy of care.

Abstract 7

The Role of Cancer Registries in Health Policy: From Data to Action

Rola rejestrów nowotworów w polityce zdrowotnej: od danych do działania.

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Keywords: cancer registry; health policy; artificial intelligence; cancer trends

Introduction: Population-based cancer registries play a strategic role in shaping evidence-based health policy in healthcare. Importantly, data from the Polish National Cancer Registry(KRN) should be distinguished from administrative or billing data, such as those collected by the National Health Fund(NFZ). NFZ datasets serve primarily to assess healthcare system workload and financial flows, while KRN data are epidemiologically validated and standardized according to international rules (ENCR, IARC, WHO). Therefore, only registry-based indicators provide an accurate and comparable picture of cancer incidence, mortality, and survival for public health and scientific purposes.

Data and methodology: The analysis is based on the operational and analytical experience of the Greater Poland Cancer Registry(GPCR), integrated into eKRN+ system. The study reviews how registry data inform regional and national oncology strategies, identify inequalities in access to care, and enable projections of future incidence and resource demand, include trend analyses or survival monitoring.

Results: In Poland, the KRN is undergoing continuous digital transformation, combining national data integration with advanced analytical capabilities. The system increasingly incorporates artificial intelligence methods, including natural language processing(NLP) models, to extract structured information from unstandardized clinical documents and automate integration with hospital information systems(HIS). These innovations significantly expand the registry's role—from retrospective data reporting toward real-time monitoring and proactive support for policy decisions. This paper presents the role of cancer registries in supporting health policy, crisis response, and forecasting healthcare needs. Registry-based analyses have provided a comprehensive understanding of cancer burden and dynamics in Poland. GPCR and KRN data enable long-term trend analyses of incidence and mortality, detailed evaluation of site-specific and sex-specific patterns, age at diagnosis, and survival outcomes. These findings reveal temporal shifts in disease profiles, changes in age distribution, and improvements in survival for selected cancer types, offering a robust basis for national planning and forecasting. The implementation of AI tools and automated HIS integration further enhances data completeness, timeliness, and analytical capacity, enabling real-time insight into cancer epidemiology and service needs.

Conclusions: Cancer registries are not only repositories of epidemiological data but key instruments of health governance. Their growing analytical and technological capabilities—supported by AI and digital interoperability—enhance efficiency in healthcare by identifying unmet needs and ensuring equal access to high-quality cancer care. Strengthening the integration between registries, clinical systems, and public health authorities is crucial to sustain a resilient, data-driven, and socially just oncology system.

Political and social transformations and health

Abstract 8

From preparation to action: Pilot Implementation of the Patient Navigation Model in Poland within the CO-CAPTAIN project

Od koncepcji do działania: pilotażowa implementacja Modelu Nawigacji Pacjenta w Polsce w ramach projektu Co-Captain

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Keywords: Patient Navigation, implementation science, cancer prevention, mental health

Introduction: The incidence of cancer is only slightly higher among people experiencing mental ill-health (PMIH), yet mortality rates are higher. Preventive lifestyle interventions have proven to be cost-effective, but identified factors may hinder effective cancer prevention at the individual, provider and system levels. CO-CAPTAIN project aims to implement Patient Navigation Model (PNM) to overcome cancer inequalities and facilitate primary cancer prevention for PMIH.

Data and methodology: Following the adaptation phase of PNM using participatory methods, a navigation-based intervention for PMIH has been implemented in Poland since June 2024. The Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR) and the Reach, Effectiveness, Adoption, Implementation, and Maintenance (RE-AIM) models were used. Measures are taken at the baseline (T0), after 6 weeks (T1) and at the end of the intervention (T2). The intervention is conducted by four Patient Navigators (PNs) in three pilot centres in Lodz.

Results: A total of 558 potential participants were approached so far, of whom 96 were recruited (M=24; F=72; Age $\bar{x}=43,3\pm 12,5$; mostly F30-F40 diagnoses). During the intervention, 29 participants withdrew from the programme for various reasons (including loss of contact/lack of engagement or voluntary withdrawal). Interventions most often focus on physical activity (including offering educational materials, participation in free classes, simple exercises to do at home, gym memberships, yoga sessions, etc.) and nutrition (educational materials, diet plans, nutritional consultations, use of nutrition apps), followed by smoking cessation and other risky health behaviours.

Conclusions: Patient Navigation is an example of skill-mixed innovation, introducing a new role and tasks in health and social care. The next stage of the project is to assess the impact of the intervention on quality of life and its cost-effectiveness, thereby enabling an estimation of its potential applicability in European health care systems.

Abstract 9

MODERN TRENDS IN POPULATION AGING: GLOBAL AND NATIONAL CONTEXT

WSPÓŁCZESNE TRENDY W STARZENIU SIĘ LUDNOŚCI: KONTEKST GLOBALNY I NARODOWY

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Keywords: aging, demographic burden, proportion of elderly population, mortality, birth rate.

Introduction: Population aging is an important demographic trend with profound social and economic implications. This process is driven by increasing life expectancy and declining birth rates, leading to an imbalance in the age structure. The study aimed to determine changes in the age structure of Ukraine’s population as a factor shaping medical and social needs.

Data and methodology: The study employed bibliosemantic, informational-analytical, and medical-statistical methods. Data from the State Statistics Service of Ukraine for 2015–2021 and the WHO European “Health for All” database were analyzed.

Results: An analysis of global statistics indicates an increase in the number of people aged over 60 years by 57.9% and those over 65 years by 58.4% between 2010 and 2024. In the WHO European Region, the share of the population aged over 60 increased from 15.6% to 19.4% between 2015 and 2020. For Ukraine, aging is primarily driven by low birth rates. An analysis of demographic data revealed that between 2015 and 2021, the share of children in the population structure remained nearly unchanged, while the share of people aged over 60 increased (from 21.8% to 24.8%) and the share of the working-age population decreased (from 62.3% to 59.2%). Significant regional variation in the aging coefficient was observed (18.5%–33.0%). The situation is aggravated by a persistent decline in birth rates (–31.8%) and an increase in mortality (+24.2%). Since 2022, adverse medical and demographic trends have intensified due to Russian military aggression, occupation of parts of the territory, and large-scale forced migration.

Conclusions: The study employed bibliosemantic, informational-analytical, and medical-statistical methods. Data from the State Statistics Service of Ukraine for 2015–2021 and the WHO European “Health for All” database were analyzed.

Abstract 10

The Invisible Epidemic of FAS/FASD – Analysis of Population Data from the Lower Silesian Voivodeship (2010–2025)

Niewidzialna epidemia FAS/FASD – analiza danych populacyjnych z województwa dolnośląskiego (2010–2025)

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Keywords: Fetal Alcohol Syndrome; FASD; epidemiology; healthcare services;

Introduction: Introduction: Fetal Alcohol Syndrome (FAS) and Fetal Alcohol Spectrum Disorders (FASD) represent some of the most serious yet underestimated neurodevelopmental disorders in children. They are directly caused by prenatal alcohol exposure and are entirely preventable. Despite estimated prevalence rates of approximately 20 per 1,000 children for FASD and 4 per 1,000 for FAS in Poland, the country lacks a centralized registry, and available epidemiological data remain fragmented and limited. This study examines population-level data from the Lower Silesian Voivodeship to characterize the current state of FAS/FASD diagnosis and healthcare provision over a 15-year period.

Data and methodology: This retrospective analysis utilized administrative healthcare data from the Lower Silesian Branch of the National Health Fund (NFZ) covering the period from 2010 through July 2025. The dataset included all recorded healthcare services provided to children with ICD-10 codes Q86.0 (Fetal Alcohol Syndrome) and P04.3 (Fetal exposure to alcohol), totaling 1,433 unique children. Since FASD lacks a dedicated ICD-10 code, this combined group (Q86.0 and P04.3) served as the operational definition for the study population. Anonymized patient identifiers enabled linkage between children and their mothers where possible, though maternal data proved largely incomplete. The analysis focused on temporal trends in diagnosis frequency, age distribution at diagnosis, types of healthcare services utilized, and system-level barriers to comprehensive care.

Results: The number of diagnosed FAS/FASD cases showed a marked upward trend, rising from 16 cases in 2010 to 236 in 2024. The mean age at diagnosis was 5.9 years (SD = 2.7), with 44% of diagnoses occurring among school-age children (7–12 years), and only 9% among children under 3 years. Healthcare services were highly fragmented across multiple specialties: genetics (40–45%), neonatology (15–20%), pediatric neurology (10–15%), rehabilitation (5–10%), and primary care (10–15%). Maternal data linkage was possible for only about 3% of cases, severely limiting the assessment of maternal risk factors and prevention opportunities.

Conclusions: This study reveals a substantial increase in FAS/FASD diagnoses in Lower Silesia, suggesting improved detection capacity, though the numbers likely remain underestimated. The relatively late average age at diagnosis (5.9 years) indicates critical gaps in early identification systems, as most children are diagnosed only when developmental deficits become apparent in school settings. The fragmented nature of care delivery, lack of coordinated diagnostic–therapeutic pathways, and limitations in data reporting systems represent significant barriers to effective management of FASD. Establishing a national FAS/FASD registry, implementing early screening programs for at-risk infants, creating integrated care pathways, and enhancing prevention efforts targeting pregnant women are essential steps to address this invisible epidemic.

Abstract 11

Women Living With Chronic Diseases: A Self-Management Program Addressing Health Inequalities

Kobiety Doświadczające Przewlekłych Chorób: Program samodzielnego zarządzania zdrowiem w odpowiedzi na nierówności zdrowotne.

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Keywords: Chronic disease; Health education; Self management; Women

Introduction: Chronic conditions and age-related health problems are a significant public health issue among postmenopausal women, who are often underdiagnosed or undertreated. Providing practical self-management tools, such as the Trauma & Chronic Disease Self-Management Program, can empower women to monitor better and manage their health, improve coping skills, and enhance overall well-being.

Data and methodology: The intervention consisted of six 2.5-hour group sessions focused on health education, self-efficacy, emotional regulation, and coping with chronic illness. Data were collected using standardised self-report questionnaires assessing pain, fatigue, sleep quality (visual analogue scale), depressive symptoms (Patient Health Questionnaire 9), stress coping strategies (MiniCOPE) and self-efficacy (the Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy Scales (Original 33-Item)).

Results: The study involved 140 older women (mean age 68.5 years) who completed at least four out of six workshop sessions. Significant improvements were observed across several health-related domains. Pain intensity significantly decreased ($p=0.006$), as did fatigue levels ($p=0.038$). Sleep quality improved notably ($p<0.001$), and symptoms of depression were reduced ($p=0.003$). Participants also demonstrated significant gains in coping strategies. In particular, improvements were observed in positive reappraisal ($p=0.029$), seeking emotional ($p=0.021$) and instrumental support ($p<0.001$), and active coping ($p=0.007$). Self-efficacy also improved significantly, including managing symptoms ($p<0.001$), coping with depressive symptoms ($p<0.001$), and maintaining social activity despite illness ($p=0.004$).

Conclusions: Participation in the program was associated with reductions in pain, fatigue, sleep problems, and depressive symptoms, as well as improvements in adaptive stress coping strategies. These results suggest that self-management interventions can empower older women to manage chronic conditions better, supporting their physical and mental well-being and highlighting their potential role in public health initiatives.

Abstract 12

Nutrition facts and myths in the opinion of the academic community

Fakty i mity żywieniowe w opinii społeczności akademickiej

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Keywords: Nutrition, students, employees, views, KomPAN

Introduction: Views on food and nutrition play a key role in shaping health behaviors. Analyzing views on food and nutrition allows for a better understanding of the factors that shape health attitudes and identifies areas requiring more intensive education. The aim of the study was to assess beliefs about food and nutrition among students and employees of the Medical University of Silesia.

Data and methodology: The study was conducted using part C of the KomPAN questionnaire, which contains statements about views on food and nutrition. Respondents were asked to determine whether a given statement was true, false, or difficult to say. Correct answers were assigned a value of one point, and the results were added up. Based on the total number of points, participants were classified into one of three categories of nutritional knowledge.

Results: An analysis of self-assessment of nutritional knowledge showed that both students and employees rated it at a similar level. In both groups, 41% of respondents considered their nutritional knowledge to be good. The obtained results are confirmed by an analysis of the accuracy of responses in the part of the questionnaire concerning views on food and nutrition. Based on the assessment of the accuracy of the statements, it was determined that 41% of employees and 46% of students had good nutritional knowledge. Sufficient knowledge was noted in 56% of employees and 53% of students, respectively.

Conclusions: Despite the medical profile of the studied population, some participants still hold misconceptions or are uncertain about the accuracy of certain nutritional statements. The results indicate a need for nutrition education in the academic community as well. The data obtained may serve as a starting point for planning educational and preventative activities aimed at raising the nutritional awareness of future healthcare professionals.

Public health in the face of 21st-century threats

Abstract 13

CONCEPTUAL APPROACHES TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF A MODERN POPULATION HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM

KONCEPCYJNE PODEJŚCIA DO ROZWOJU NOWOCZESNEGO SYSTEMU MONITOROWANIA ZDROWIA POPULACJI

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Keywords: health monitoring, system, principles, data needs, requirements

Introduction: Population health monitoring is a key instrument for making effective management decisions in the healthcare sector. The development of the public health system in Ukraine necessitates the establishment of a modern health monitoring system aligned with the strategic directions of state policy, existing challenges, and international best practices.

Data and methodology: The study analyzed scientific literature, strategic and programmatic documents of the WHO and the WHO European Region, as well as regulatory frameworks of several countries regarding population health monitoring. A survey of public health professionals was conducted to identify their information needs related to population health. Bibliographic, informational-analytical, and medical-statistical methods were applied.

Results: The analysis of health monitoring practices in the USA, Canada, Japan, Australia, and EU countries (Austria, Poland, and Sweden) revealed both strengths and existing challenges of monitoring studies, providing valuable insights for the development of the Ukrainian system. An analysis of Ukraine's national regulatory framework demonstrated the presence of a multi-level, integrated monitoring system and its active development. However, the system faces numerous challenges due to military actions, insufficient data integration, issues with data quality and reliability, limited funding, inadequate analytical capacity, and the need for modernization. A sociological survey among public health professionals revealed a lack of data on social and mental health, work with high-risk groups, socio-economic determinants, occupational diseases and safety, non-communicable diseases, and behavioral risk factors. Additional issues were found in the use of data for decision-making, program development, and policy justification, as well as a need for continuous professional development among specialists in health monitoring.

Conclusions: The priority task is to develop a modern system for population health monitoring that aligns with the strategic directions of national healthcare development, complies with the requirements and recommendations of international health organizations, incorporates the best global practices, and addresses the needs of public health professionals and healthcare managers.

Abstract 14

Factors associated with the use of selected health services among adults aged 18-64 in Poland

Czynniki związane z korzystaniem z wybranych usług zdrowotnych wśród dorosłych w wieku 18-64 lat w Polsce

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Keywords: healthcare services; healthcare utilization; healthcare;

Introduction: Mandatory health insurance system in Poland, provides universal access to health services, including medical consultations and a set of diagnostic tests. This study aimed to identify factors associated with not visiting doctors and not performing diagnostic tests in the last 12 months among a representative sample of Poles aged 18-64.

Data and methodology: A cross-sectional survey was carried out in December 2024. A total of 5006 adults aged 18-64 years completed a series of questionnaires (computer-assisted web interviews, CAWI) on health-related behaviors and health inequalities.

Results: Among respondents, 22.4% had not visited a doctor of any specialty (excluding dentists) in the past 12 months, and 19% had not undergone any diagnostic tests during that period. Men (AOR=1.57; 95% CI:1.35–1.83; $p<0.001$), individuals without higher education ($p < 0.05$), those without chronic diseases ($p<0.05$), people aged 35–44 years (AOR=1.22; 95% CI:1.00–1.50; $p<0.05$), those who were single or in informal relationships ($p<0.05$), individuals without full-time employment ($p<0.05$), and those living in very poor economic conditions (AOR=1.44; 95% CI:1.09–1.92; $p<0.05$) were more likely to avoid visiting doctors in the past 12 months.

Conclusions: In Poland, social inequalities continue to affect willingness to use health services.

Abstract 15

Parental Attitudes Toward HPV Vaccination - An Analysis of Factors Influencing Parental Decisions

Postawy rodziców wobec szczepień przeciwko wirusowi HPV - analiza czynników wpływających na decyzje rodzicielskie

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Keywords: parental attitudes, HPV vaccination, HPV knowledge, health education

Introduction: Human Papillomavirus (HPV) is one of the main risk factors for the development of cervical cancer and other genital cancers. HPV vaccination is an effective preventive method. In Poland, despite the availability of vaccines, awareness of their importance in cancer prevention remains low. The aim of

this study was to analyze parental attitudes toward HPV vaccination, considering the demographic and social factors influencing their decisions.

Data and methodology: The study was conducted using a diagnostic survey method with a questionnaire filled out by parents of children in primary school (grades 1–8). Statistical analysis was performed using the STATISTICA v. 13 program.

Results: The study results indicate that parental attitudes toward HPV vaccination vary depending on education level, age, and knowledge about the virus. Parents with a higher level of education were more likely to express willingness to vaccinate their children ($p = 0.03$). Additionally, parents who had prior exposure to information about HPV showed greater openness to vaccination ($p = 0.04$). Statistical analysis revealed a significant relationship between willingness to vaccinate and concerns about vaccine safety ($p = 0.02$). Specifically, parents who were concerned about side effects were more likely to express doubts about vaccination, which was confirmed at a statistically significant level. Furthermore, the results indicate that younger parents (aged 25–35) were more open to vaccination than older parents, which also showed statistical significance ($p = 0.05$).

Conclusions: Health education and increased awareness about HPV may contribute to a higher number of parents deciding to vaccinate their children. It is important for public health institutions and schools to focus on disseminating accurate information about the benefits of HPV vaccination.

Abstract 16

Public Health Challenges in the 21st Century: The Threat of Infectious Disease Resurgence Driven by Vaccine Hesitancy and Misinformation

Wyzwania zdrowia publicznego w XXI wieku: Zagrożenie nawrotem chorób zakaźnych spowodowane wahaniem wobec szczepień i dezinformacją

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Keywords: Vaccination, Vaccine Hesitancy, Public Health, Misinformation, Parental Attitudes

Introduction: Protective vaccinations are a cornerstone of public health, offering the most effective instrument for reducing the incidence and mortality rates of communicable diseases. Despite this proven efficacy, a global challenge has emerged in the form of a systematic decline in vaccine confidence, primarily fueled by misinformation and insufficient communication from medical personnel. This trend jeopardizes epidemiological stability, posing a direct threat to achieving goals like the WHO Measles Elimination Program. This study aimed to analyze parental knowledge and attitudes toward vaccinations against diseases such as measles and pertussis, thereby identifying crucial barriers to optimal immunization coverage in a regional context.

Data and methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted in Central Poland (Radomsko) between January and March 2025, involving 459 parents of primary school students. The methodology combined two stages: a questionnaire survey utilizing the validated Vaccination Attitudes Examination (VAX) scale to assess skepticism, alongside the analysis of official measles and pertussis vaccination coverage data for children born between 2014 and 2019, acquired from the State Sanitary Inspectorate. The VAX scale measured four dimensions of skepticism, including concerns about unforeseen future effects and mistrust of vaccine benefits. Statistical associations between knowledge levels, attitudes, and vaccination status were determined using Pearson's chi-square test and odds ratios (OR).

Results: Significant knowledge gaps were identified among parents, despite high declared awareness (97%), with less than half (44%) considering vaccination information sufficiently accessible. High parental mistrust (VAX scale) was found to be the strongest predictor of vaccine refusal. Among parents with high mistrust, only 75.3% of children completed all mandatory vaccinations, contrasting sharply with 99.7% completion among those with low mistrust (OR=0.0084; $p < 0.000001$). Furthermore, worries about unforeseen future effects were the most prevalent concern, affecting 63.0% of respondents.

Conclusions: Substantial parental knowledge deficits and deep-seated mistrust constitute critical barriers to achieving optimal vaccination coverage, contributing to the declining immunization rates observed locally. Given the rising influence of social media in spreading misinformation, there is an urgent need to strengthen the role of medical professionals (physicians, nurses) as the most trusted sources of reliable information. Future public health interventions must prioritize rebuilding confidence through personalized risk communication and targeted educational strategies.

Abstract 17

Sociodemographic differences in the use of dietary supplements in a representative sample of 5006 adults of working age Poland

Czynniki determinujące używanie suplementów diety wśród 5006 dorosłych w wieku produkcyjnym w Polsce

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Keywords: dietary supplementation; diet supplements; diet; supplementation

Introduction: Dietary supplements are products that are concentrated sources of vitamins, minerals, or other substances with a nutritional or physiological effect. This study aimed to identify sociodemographic differences in the use of dietary supplements in a representative sample of Poles aged 18-64 years.

Data and methodology: This study is based on dataset generated during the representative cross-sectional survey (December 2024) carried out among 5006 adults aged 18-64 years in Poland. Attitudes towards use of dietary supplements were assessed.

Results: Among all respondents, 39.1% declared regular use of dietary supplements in the three months preceding the present study, and another 31.5% reported occasional use. Among those who used supplements in the three months preceding the study, 11.4% had all of their supplements prescribed by a doctor, and another 22.7% had some of them. Gender, age, educational level, place of residence, number of infections per year and following diet were associated ($p < 0.05$), with the regular use of dietary supplements in the last 3 months preceding the survey.

Conclusions: This study revealed that the majority of working-age adults in Poland use dietary supplements, but only one-third of dietary supplement users consult with a doctor. Educational and law interventions are needed.

Abstract 18

The relationship between food and skin allergy in children and adolescents and atmospheric air pollution in Bielsko-Biala

Związek alergii pokarmowej i skórnej u dzieci i młodzieży z zanieczyszczeniem powietrza atmosferycznego w Bielsku-Białej

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Keywords: food allergies, skin allergies, air pollution, suspended dust PM10, benzo(a)pyrene.

Introduction: The increase in the incidence of allergic diseases is also caused by environmental conditions, including air pollution. In Europe and the USA, the incidence of food allergies is 6% and 8% of children, respectively. In 2023, the Chief Inspectorate of Environmental Protection (GIOŚ) stated that the air quality is much better compared to the previous 5 years.

Data and methodology: Based on data from the Department of Health of the Silesian Voivodeship Office in Katowice, tables were prepared to illustrate the incidence of allergic contact dermatitis caused by substances introduced into the body (L 27) and allergic food inflammation of the stomach, small intestine and colon (K 52.2). In order to correlate the average annual concentrations of selected air pollutants and the incidence of food and skin allergies, the Statistica 13.6.0.064 (0616) program and Pearson correlation coefficients were used.

Results: The incidence of food and skin allergies is decreasing and is 164.4/10,000 in 2018 and 150.6/10,000 in 2022 for food allergies and 197.3/10,000 in 2018 and 181.1/10,000 in 2022 for skin allergies. The average annual concentration of PM10 and benzo(a)pyrene is decreasing.

Conclusions: In the analyzed time period, the discussed average annual concentrations of substances were not exceeded. The decreasing incidence of both food and skin allergies is related to the improvement in atmospheric air quality.

Abstract 19

Analysis of the incidence of asthma among pupils of primary schools in Bielsko-Biala located in areas with various degrees of industrialization

Analiza częstości występowania astmy wśród uczniów szkół podstawowych w Bielsku-Białej położonych na terenach o różnym stopniu uprzemysłowienia

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Keywords: asthma, air pollution, industrial plants, chronic disease, children.

Introduction: Close proximity to industrial plants is considered a factor in the development of asthma, mainly in children. Approximately 13% of the global incidence of childhood asthma can be attributed to traffic-related air pollution (TRAP). In Bielsko-Biala, industrial plants are located in the Komorowice and Wapienica districts (including machinery, automotive, metallurgical and food industries), which results in pollution of the local natural environment.

Data and methodology: In February 2024, with the consent of the principals of primary schools (SP 22, SP 26, SP 28, SP 29, SP 32, SP 36) in Bielsko-Biala, data were obtained on the number of students of grades VI–VIII (without sensitive data) who had bronchial asthma diagnosed by a doctor. The school hygienist collects medical information about the health of each student in the health card, which is obtained from parents. Based on the collected data (without sensitive data), a table was prepared illustrating the epidemiology of asthma among children.

Results: The analyzed primary schools have 927 students in grades VI–VIII, including 157 with asthma. There are 122 students with asthma in Primary School 29 and Primary School 32, which are located in industrial zones.

Conclusions: The place of residence is important for the occurrence of asthma. Living close to industrial plants contributes to the development of the disease (unlike the outskirts of the city).

Public health potential in the system

Abstract 20

From Lifestyle to Self-Worth - Lessons from the Blue Zones for Public Health

Od stylu życia do poczucia wartości - lekcje Blue Zones dla zdrowia publicznego

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Keywords: Blue Zones, lifestyle, self-esteem, public health, mental health

Introduction: The Blue Zones concept is associated with regions where residents are characterised by longevity and well-being. The lifestyle of these populations includes a healthy diet, physical activity, social connections, purpose in life, and stress management. Research suggests that these practices affect health, including self-esteem. The aim of the study is to assess how adherence to the Blue Zones lifestyle principles affects self-esteem.

Data and methodology: The study was conducted using the CAWI method between August 2024 and June 2025. The sample consisted of 377 participants aged 15- 91 (68.4% woman). A proprietary questionnaire covered socio-demographic data, lifestyle, activity, social relationships, stress, and self-esteem, assessed using the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale and a 16-point Blue Zones compliance scale. Data were analysed with Statistica 13.3.

Results: The study revealed a significant positive correlation between higher adherence to the Blue Zones lifestyle and increased self-esteem ($p<0.05$). The highest proportion of participants with high and very high self-esteem was observed among those who engages in daily physical activity (41.1%). Logistic regression analysis further confirmed that self-esteem was strongly associated with physical activity ($p<0.001$).

Conclusions: A lifestyle inspired by the Blue Zones concept may positive influence an individual's self-esteem, even within a highly urbanised society such as Poland. Since mental health is closely linked to physical well-being, psychological interventions aimed at enhancing self-esteem may contribute to overall health improvement and, consequently, a reduced risk of illness through the implementation of Blue Zones principles.

Abstract 21

Healthy ageing in the digital age – mobile applications for seniors as a preventive tool

Zdrowe starzenie w erze cyfrowej – aplikacje mobilne dla seniorów jako narzędzie profilaktyki

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Keywords: mobile applications, seniors, healthy ageing, prevention, mHealth

Introduction: The ageing of modern societies poses growing challenges for healthcare systems due to chronic diseases and functional limitations in older people. In this context, mobile applications represent a promising tool to support healthy ageing by promoting activity, self-monitoring and prevention. The aim was to analyse the use of mobile applications in preventive healthcare for older people, highlighting their advantages, challenges and factors influencing effective implementation.

Data and methodology: The analysis covered the latest systematic reviews and meta-analyses (from 2023 to 2025) on mobile health (mHealth) applications for older adults, including interventions in the areas of physical activity, sedentary behaviour reduction, and chronic diseases. A review of available publications was used, searched mainly in PubMed and Web of Science databases. Quantitative analysis of the results was also necessary, as well as a qualitative assessment of the functionality and design of the applications.

Results: A review of studies has shown that mobile health apps support older adults. Using mHealth apps clearly reduces time spent sitting. On average, users sat about an hour less per day than non-users. Diabetes-focused apps also helped seniors, leading to better HbA_{1c} levels, an indicator of glucose control. A similar improvement appeared in physical activity. App users took roughly 800 more steps daily than those in the control group. The quality of apps for seniors, including memory and cognitive-training programmes, was also evaluated. Among 24 apps, only a few earned very high ratings. The average score was 3.57 out of 5, with the lowest results in user-engagement features. This highlights the need to design apps more effectively for older adults and their motivations.

Conclusions: Mobile applications are a promising tool for supporting healthy ageing by increasing physical activity, reducing sedentary behaviour and aiding chronic disease management. Their full potential depends on age-friendly design and interdisciplinary collaboration to ensure digital prevention is truly effective.

Abstract 22

Building bridges in healthcare: enhancing communication and shared decision-making for better patient outcomes

Wzmacnianie komunikacji i wspólnego podejmowania decyzji w opiece zdrowotnej - klucz do lepszych wyników leczenia

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Keywords: communication skills, family physicians, patient-centered care, shared decision-making, medical education

Introduction: Health communication and shared decision-making (SDM) are essential elements of patient-centered care, playing a key role in the healthcare decision-making process. Communication skills, considered one of the most important aspects of professionalism, can significantly influence patient compliance and treatment outcomes. In turn, involving patients in decision-making can reduce decision regret and anxiety about treatment choices, improve treatment outcomes, patient satisfaction and quality of life, and the quality and safety of healthcare. The aim of the study was to assess the communication skills of family physicians and review the current literature to identify the most important barriers and facilitators to the use of SDM from the perspective of the physician and the patient.

Data and methodology: The study was conducted using the Computer-Assisted Telephone Interview (CATI) method on a representative sample of family physicians. To assess communication skills, the Interpersonal Communication Skills Inventory (Learning Dynamics, 2002) was used. Four key areas of communication were examined: sending clear messages, listening, giving and receiving feedback, and managing emotional interactions. To identify the barriers and facilitators of SDM, a scoping review of literature from the past five years was conducted in June 2024, following the PRISMA-ScR guidelines.

Results: A total of 600 family physicians participated in the study. Of the respondents, 94.5% rated their communication skills as good or very good. According to the Interpersonal Communication Skills Inventory, strong communication areas accounted for 24.8%, while areas requiring improvement or attention constituted 75.2%. The strongest area identified was sending clear messages (54.8%), followed by managing emotional interactions (27.2%), giving and receiving feedback (20.5%), and listening (13.8%). The most commonly reported barriers for SDM include: lack of time and excessive patient workload, absence of a culture and tradition of SDM, a paternalistic model of healthcare, patients' passive attitudes, and a lack of confidence in their ability to participate in decision-making. Key facilitators of SDM include trust, the use of educational materials by physicians, the belief that SDM leads to better health outcomes, and communication skills training for healthcare providers.

Conclusions: The communication skills of Polish family physicians require special attention, especially in the areas of active listening and giving and receiving feedback. The results suggest that significant improvement in these skills may require dedicated training. Given the well-documented benefits of implementing SDM—even though it is a challenge for public health, requiring time and systemic adjustments—efforts should be made to overcome existing barriers.

Abstract 23

MODERN ASPECTS OF PUBLIC HEALTH SPECIALIST TRAINING

NOWOCZESNE ASPEKTY SZKOLENIA SPECJALISTÓW ZDROWIA PUBLICZNEGO

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Keywords: educational program, public health, challenges and threats, directions for improvement, academic disciplines

Introduction: Under current challenges and threats to population health, the training of public health specialists capable of addressing complex tasks in the development and implementation of effective health policies is of particular importance. The aim of the study is to identify the directions for improving the educational program for training Masters of Public Health, taking into account existing challenges and problems.

Data and methodology: The study employed bibliosemantic, information-analytical, medical-statistical, sociological methods. The program involved analysis of scientific literature sources concerning public health challenges, WHO and ASPHER documents on public health priorities, sociological surveys among graduates of the Master’s program in Public Health regarding the quality of education and labor market integration, as well as improvement of the educational program for Master’s degree training in Public Health.

Results: The study of graduates’ opinions on the quality of the educational program “Public Health” demonstrated a high evaluation: 82.4% of respondents indicated overall satisfaction, 93.8% noted acquisition of deep theoretical knowledge and necessary practical skills, and 100% confirmed the formation of required competencies. At the same time, graduates expressed wishes for program optimization to better meet the practical needs of their professional activities. The training content was improved through in-depth study of the use of health monitoring data for public health policymaking; responses to new demographic challenges, particularly aging and migration; addressing health inequalities; and implementing the “One Health” and “Health in All Policies” approaches. Given the active development of e-Health, the program was supplemented with a new course, “Digital Transformation of Healthcare.” Globalization processes led to the inclusion of new disciplines: “Global Health” and “Healthcare in International Humanitarian Law.”

Conclusions: Improving the educational program for training Masters of Public Health in line with new challenges and threats will contribute to the acquisition of competencies necessary for graduates to effectively develop and implement public health policies.

Abstract 24

The Latest Developments in the Czech Public Health

Najnowsze wydarzenia w czeskim zdrowiu publicznym

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Keywords: public health, Czech Republic, health system resilience, health in all policies, prevention

Since the 1990s, public health in the Czech Republic has been mostly understood as the provision of health services to already ill individuals and traditional hygienic services. Health promotion and, in particular, the "health in all policies" strategy remain rare topics in political debate and are not widely implemented in practice. The presentation highlights key trends and challenges shaping Czech public health in recent years in the post-pandemic era. Despite some success stories, many good intentions remain only as plans and are still too medically oriented.

Abstract 25

The Role of Mobile Media in Shaping Health-Promoting Attitudes among Youth Aged 15-20

Rola mediów mobilnych w kształtowaniu postaw prozdrowotnych młodzieży w wieku 15–20 lat

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Keywords: adolescent health, digital technologies, internet, health behaviours

Introduction: Digital technologies can be both an opportunity and a threat in shaping pro-health attitudes among young people because, on the one hand, they provide access to reliable sources of information, expert blogs, applications, and educational platforms, which supports the development of young people's health knowledge, but on the other hand, there is a risk of internet addiction, exposure to misinformation, and excessive exposure to social pressure related to appearance and lifestyle.

Data and methodology: The study was conducted on a group of 1,019 respondents (689 girls and 330 boys) aged 15–20, high school students in the Silesian Province. A proprietary paper-based questionnaire was used to conduct the research. The collected data was statistically analyzed using the chi-square (χ^2) test and Fisher's test.

Results: Most of the respondents, regardless of gender, spend more than four hours a day on the Internet. Younger people spend more time on the Internet than their older peers. No statistically significant relationship between gender and time spent online was found. A significant relationship between age and place of residence and time spent on the Internet was found. Young people from rural areas spend less time on the Internet and are more likely to declare that they do not use the Internet. Sources of health information vary depending on gender and age; girls are more likely to use expert websites, such as Wikipedia or poradnikzdrowie.pl, while boys prefer social media and YouTube. Girls are more likely to name coaches and healthy lifestyle advocates as their role models, while boys prefer athletes.

Conclusions: Research shows that young people spend a significant part of their day on the internet, and their behaviour varies in many ways depending on their age, gender, and place of residence.

Varia (other)

Abstract 26

Awareness of the importance of reflectors and the safety of children and young people

Świadomość znaczenia odblasków a bezpieczeństwo dzieci i młodzieży

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Keywords: Reflectors, Road safety, Awareness, Children and young people, Pedestrians

Introduction: Pedestrian safety on the road, especially for children and young people, is a key social issue, as indicated by alarming road accident statistics. Reflective elements significantly increase pedestrian visibility, enabling drivers to react more quickly, but despite numerous campaigns, their use remains low. The aim of this study was to examine the level of knowledge among children and young people about the importance of reflectors in improving road safety and to identify the factors influencing their use. The analysis also aimed to determine the extent to which theoretical awareness translates into the practical use of reflectors.

Data and methodology: The study was quantitative and was conducted using an anonymous survey. A total of 542 respondents from different age groups took part: primary school pupils (grades 1-3 and 4-8), high school pupils, and public health students. A proprietary questionnaire was used in three versions, adapted to the age of the respondents, to collect data on their knowledge, attitudes, and actual use of reflective elements.

Results: The analysis showed a very high level of theoretical knowledge about reflectors and their function in all groups, with, for example, 97% of students correctly identifying their importance. Nevertheless, a clear difference was observed between awareness and actual behavior—the regularity of reflector use decreases with the age of the respondents. Among the youngest, the main reason for not wearing them was forgetfulness, while among teenagers and students, aesthetic factors and the desire to fit in with their peers were significant barriers.

Conclusions: The results highlight the need to move from informational education to practical habits and attitude formation, especially in older age groups. Promotional activities must consider aesthetic and psychological aspects, promoting reflectors as a fashionable and integral part of clothing and raising awareness of visibility limitations on the road. It is suggested that systematic education be implemented and that the availability of attractive and diverse reflective elements be increased to effectively improve pedestrian safety.

Abstract 27

Health education in social media – students' preferences, concerns and the role of e-health literacy

Edukacja zdrowotna w mediach społecznościowych – preferencje i obawy studentów oraz rola kompetencji zdrowotnych w zakresie e-zdrowia (e-health literacy)

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Keywords: e-health literacy; health communication; medical influencers

Introduction: Health education is increasingly delivered via social media, often by medical professionals acting as influencers. With digital platforms as major sources of health content for youth, e-health literacy—understanding and evaluating online health information—has become essential. This study explores students' habits, motivations, concerns, and literacy in navigating such content.

Data and methodology: A quantitative survey was conducted among 61 students who use social media for health information. The questionnaire covered platforms used, followed professionals, reasons for engagement, concerns, and critical assessment of health content.

Results: Instagram (93.4%) and TikTok (57.4%) were the top sources of health-related content. Students most frequently followed doctors (88.5%), nurses (37.7%), and paramedics (23%). Motivations included easy-to-understand content (83.6%), interest in private lives (45.9%), and practical tips (44.3%). Main concerns were misinformation about qualifications (55.7%), information overload (52.5%), and disinformation (36.1%). Non-medical students more often cited concern about misinformation (58.3%) than medical students (21.6%). Levels of e-health literacy varied, especially regarding credibility assessment.

Conclusions: Students actively engage with medical influencers and appreciate simplified, accessible information. However, concerns about content quality and overload remain. Promoting e-health literacy may help users make informed decisions and avoid digital misinformation. Social media is a major source of health information among students. E-health literacy helps mitigate misinformation and supports informed decision-making.

Abstract 28

Physical activity as part of adapting to chronic disease – a comparative analysis of people with type I diabetes and the healthy population

Aktywność fizyczna jako element adaptacji do choroby przewlekłej – analiza porównawcza osób z cukrzycą typu I i populacji zdrowej

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Keywords: type I diabetes, physical activity, young adults

Introduction: According to data from the International Diabetes Federation, 1 in 9 people worldwide struggle with type 1 diabetes (T1D). Living with a chronic lifestyle disease such as T1D requires adapting many aspects of daily life to cope with the condition. Regular physical activity and maintaining an optimal level of activity is important for overall health, improving glycaemic control and minimising complications of chronic disease. The aim of the study was to analyse the level of physical activity among diabetics in Poland in comparison to healthy individuals and to examine the impact of physical activity on diabetes-specific quality of life and the level of diabetic distress.

Data and methodology: The study was conducted using a diagnostic survey method with a questionnaire technique, using standardised research tools: the Global Physical Activity Questionnaire (GPAQ), the Diabetes Quality of Life Brief-Clinical Inventory (DQL-BCI) and the Diabetes Distress Scale (DDS). The age of the study population ranged from 18 to 35 years (M=24.17+4.36 years). Respondents were divided into two subgroups: patients with type I diabetes (n=120) and the healthy population (n=116).

Results: The results of our study show that diabetics have significantly lower levels of physical activity compared to healthy individuals (p=0.0002). Insufficient and sufficient levels of physical activity predominate among diabetics, while in the healthy population there is a significant predominance of people with high levels of physical activity (p<0.001). The level of physical activity has no significant correlation with diabetes-specific quality of life or the level of diabetic distress.

Conclusions: The results obtained indicate that people with T1D are characterised by significantly lower levels of physical activity compared to the healthy population. Although regular physical activity is a key element in maintaining health and controlling glycaemia, no significant relationship was found between its level and diabetes-specific quality of life or diabetes distress. These results highlight the need to intensify educational and motivational activities to promote physical activity among diabetics.

Abstract 28

Pilot Study: Digital Intervention for Cognitive Empathy in Health Professions Education – Patient Perspectives

Badanie pilotażowe: cyfrowa interwencja na rzecz empatii poznawczej w kształceniu zawodów medycznych – perspektywa pacjentów

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Keywords: cognitive empathy, digital solutions in healthcare, health professions education, innovations in teaching, psycho-social competencies

Introduction: Referring to soft skills such as empathy in the education of medical staff has long been a methodological challenge. The study aimed to identify effective methods for teaching empathy to medical students. A multi-stage research process was conducted in collaboration with Empatyzar sp. z o.o., which provided a pilot prototype of a digital solution (Empatyzar app) created to support the development of soft skills among staff of various organizations. Focus group interviews with patients over 60 years of age highlighted empathy as a crucial competency for healthcare professionals, while the Empatyzar app was simultaneously tested during classes with medical and physiotherapy students.

Data and methodology: The research design combined qualitative and experimental components. The research group consisted of 59 participants and the control group of 30 participants. Focused interviews were used to assess the need for updated educational methods, and a psychological experiment with testing was applied to evaluate the effectiveness of the app. Students assessed their agreement with proposed messages and phrases across five hypothetical scenarios using a Likert-type scale, completing the task both before and after workshops using the Empatyzar app.

Conclusions: The results appear promising: digital solutions (e.g., the Empatyzar app) can effectively support the development of soft skills. Approaches that incorporate psychological parameters (e.g., personality) may be beneficial because they refer to personal traits linked to performing tasks requiring soft skills. Further multi-center studies involving patients, students, and medical personnel are needed to establish the final design of such interventions

